

Simulation analysis of electric vehicle charging station using hybrid sources

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ABSTRACT

This paper described simulation analysis of electric vehicle (EV) charging station using hybrid sources. This paper highlights electric vehicle charging station with photovoltaic panels, batteries, and diesel generator. This study employs a solar, battery, diesel generator set, and grid electric vehicle charging station to provide continuous charging in is landed, grid-linked, and Diesel generator (DG) set connected modes. By utilizing a solar and battery, the charging of battery in electric vehicle application is the primary objective. If the storage battery is poor and there is no solar generation, the mode of charging automatically shifted to grid or diesel generator set. Furthermore, the charging station manages the generator voltage and frequency without the need of a mechanical speed governor in conjunction with the storage battery. The demand is nonlinear at unity power factor (UPF). For continuous charging, power used from the grid or the DG set and it is synchronized to the grid/generator voltage by the point of common coupling voltage. To boost charging station operating efficiency, the charging station also performs all power transfer from car to grid, vehicle to house, and vehicle to vehicle.

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1. INTRODUCTION

With zero tailpipe emissions, electric vehicle are the most efficient modes of transportation. Given the benefits of electric vehicles (EVs), there are presently 3 million vehicles on the road, with a total of 100 million expected by 2030. However, the proposed approach needs a vast charging infrastructure as well as massive energy. Furthermore, using fossil fuels to create energy, on the other hand, does not reduce emissions; it only moves them from vehicles to power plants. As a consequence, employing nonconventional energy sources for electricity generation may completely eliminate emissions while simultaneously benefiting the environment. solar production is the most feasible option for electric vehicle charging in all sources because it is available practically anywhere, whether rural or urban [1]–[3]. It is open almost all year

set connected charging in Figure 5. Following parameters has been selected for simulation. Table 1 shows simulation parameters.

The CS's uninterruptible functioning results demonstrate in Figure 5. Initially in islanded mode, PV array electricity provided the charge to EVs linked at PCC. The excess generation is stored in the energy storage due to exceed charging needs of the EVs. In 0.8 s, sun irradiation decreases from 1000 W/m² to 300 W/m². So, the PV array output decreases and the storage battery begins to discharge in order to maintain uninterrupted charging. At 1 s, the storage battery empties as the PV array power drops to zero. The controller connects the CS to the grid for synchronization after the battery has been completely discharged. The simulation results indicate the different mode of operation. At 0.8 s phase, grid and storage battery power are unavailable The CS began taking electricity from the grid. The charging station automatically changes modes based on generation and demand is seen in Figure 5.

Figure 2. Simulation model of EV charging station using hybrid sources

Figure 3. EV charging by solar

Figure 4. EV charging by grid

Figure 5. Diesel generator set connected charging

System	Specification
Grid connected	1 Phase, 230 V, 50 Hz
Lead-acid battery	360 Volt, 14 Ah
PV array	1 Kilowatt
EV1 AC	2.6 Kw
EV2 DC	2.6 kw
Load	4.6 Kw

4. CONCLUSION

This paper described simulation analysis of electric vehicle charging station using hybrid sources such as photovoltaic panels, batteries, and diesel generator and to provide continuous charging. Charging of the battery in charging stations by the solar panel first. If battery is discharge due to solar power absent than it takes automatically power from the other two sources. In comparison with all the hybrid sources, diesel generator with good voltage quality as compare to solar and grid in EV charging station seen in the simulation results. The outcome of this paper is, diesel generator set as a feasible solution in charging station for battery charging because it can provide continuous, efficiently and economical charging.

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